

12:30 - 14:00	Session 8: Challenges for Theory, Modeling, and Synthetic Observations	Chair: Camilla Pacifici (STScI)
12:30 - 13:00	8a Invited Talk: Risa Wechsler (Stanford)	Invited Talk
13:00 - 13:15	8b Nicole Drakos (UCSC)	A Mock Catalog for a Roman Telescope Ultra Deep Field
13:15 - 13:30	8c John Weaver (Cosmic Dawn Center)	The COSMOS2020 Catalog: A stepping stone for the next generation of galaxy surveys
13:30 - 13:45	8d Prerak Garg (Univ of Florida)	Modeling nebular emission in galaxy formation simulations
13:45 - 14:00	8e Aritra Ghosh (Yale)	Studying Morphology & Quenching of Galaxies in the NGRST Era using Interpretable Convolutional Neural Networks

Session 8 live captioning on Thursday, 8 October 2020

This afternoon's session chair is Cami. Thank you everyone for connecting to the conference. We will have one invited talk and four contributed talks. The invited talk will be 25 minutes and I will give you a warning at 5 minutes before, a verbal warning, I will jump in. I will try not to be too rude. Then we will have four contributed talks, 12 minutes plus three and I will give you a warning at 2 minutes. For questions please use the slack channel. Session eight, yes, session eight channel. There will be questions coming after the talk so the speaker can go back and answer those questions. If you and the audience have a question, please wait for the speaker to answer the question first and then you can continue the conversation. Absolutely. I guess I said everything. We have the invited talk by **Risa Wechsler**. You can share your screen. We will get started. Theory, simulation, modeling challenges and opportunities and the Nancy Grace Roman era. Take it away.

It's a real pleasure to be here. Actually, preparing this talk got me even more excited than I was already about the space telescope and what it will be able to do. And I was given this sort of impossible assignment to talk about all theory, simulation and modeling challenges. I'm obviously not going to be able to cover all of those, but I thought I would start by just mentioning what I think some of the key questions are for galaxy formation in the Roman era. First, how do the history, properties, and distribution connect to the growth and distribution of dark matter? How are the black holes and galaxies coevolved? How are gas inflow and outflow driven by Halo formation and how did they drive and regulate star formation? Over what, range and redshifts, what halos re-ionize the universe? And what is the lowest Halo mass in which galaxies are able to form and how did that change over time. And then also what can galaxies teach us about the nature of dark matter. Also a really exciting question. In this talk I'm going to sort of, in the context of those questions I won't address all of them, but what roles, theory, simulations do they play? Where are we now? What opportunities will Roman data provide? And what modeling approaches, simulation tools and theory advances are really needed to take full advantage of the data? I'm going to focus on two topics. One is, how do we understand galaxy formation and its full cosmological context? Second, how do we actually modernize our analysis of these large data sets with simulations of an integral part of that analysis? I want to just briefly start with a -- first, let me just mention, we all know this, but this is going to be a really exciting era for observations of the universe. A really

vast, multifaceted observational contact. We have things in space from the ground, things and many wavelengths and what we really want to do from the perspective of building a theoretical understanding of galaxy formation is put all of these different pieces together. The Roman telescope is going to play a big role in this during the era. Just to set the stage, I will spend a few minutes here. Theoretical context. We know that given a set of cosmological parameters which are now measured incredibly well with the background and late time survey formation, we know that -- sorry, I'm not sure if the movie is playing. If you can't see the movie, this is supposed to be a simulation involving, what you are supposed to be seeing as it evolves is that as the halos pop up we can measure lots of different statistics of that underlying. We actually have now and quite a lot of detail over a very wide range scale, actually showing that structure formation as predicted from the detailed simulation is in very good agreement with observations. That is great because it provides a really amazing context for galaxy formation that has really developed over the last 15-20 years. Where we now can, based on a set of well measured cosmological parameters make very precise predictions for how galaxies or how the dark matter halos assemble over time. And then we can try to understand how galaxies get built up in those dark matter halos. There are a lot of different aspects, what physics actually goes on, hydrodynamics, black hole formation lots of feedback did these things are all actually really important. One of the things that makes galaxy formation challenging is that were trying to tie these pieces together over a wide range of data. We also have observations over a wide range of scale. I just want to mention that we've tested it over a very wide range of scales, but alternative to dark matter can still do different things, below the scales where we measured them. This is a particular interesting machine because all of these different kinds of modifications to dark matter form, interact, those can impact small-scale, but they also have an impact galaxy formation. We have this theoretical framework where galaxy formation is really driven by structure formation, it depends on the details of dark matter. But also galaxy formation itself, the process of forming galaxy feedback can influence structure formation on small scale. We really need to understand how galaxies and dark matter halos are connected and order to get the most, to learn the most about dark matter and dark energy using instruments like the Roman Space Telescope. Over the last 15 years or so a real set of approaches has evolved to model the connection between galaxies and their underlying dark matter halos. And this is a diagram that comes from a review article that I wrote with Jeremy a couple of years ago which sort of outlines this range of possibilities from full hydrodynamical simulations where you try to assimilate all the feedback, directly in a compound setting. To a more empirical approach, some of which still use the history, some use just the isolated dark matter halos as a function of time. And I think in the modern era we really want to be using a range of these approaches over different scales because we are not yet, and were quite far away from being able to simulate the volume of the universe that we can observe at a resolution. That's a really key point. I want to briefly just talk about the very simplest version of this kind of way to connect galaxies and halos and that simple way is just to say, okay, I have a set of dark matter halos and I look at the universe and I observed galaxies of different sizes or masses. And in this very simple approach I'm just connecting the most massive galaxies with the most massive Halo. And -- so then this image sort of schematic here, the top line on the left-hand side is the predicted Halo mass function, the bottom line is the observed stellar mass function of galaxies. One he put those two things together you get a relationship between galaxies stellar mass and dark Halo mass. That is obviously a listing of the interesting thing, the recent model that we have actually parameterize is the most of the complexity. Two examples of the complexity are scattered between that. Or the concentration or formation history dependent on galaxy property at the given Halo mass. And the beautiful thing is that at low red shift, with large samples, galaxy clustering properties provide a really precision, how much scatter is there between stellar mass and Halo mass at a given Halo mass, do all galaxies have the same stellar mass or does it depend on some other property? At low red shift we have the samples where we can really do those detail tests. And they actually know include clustering, galaxy lensing, clusters, and those combinations of statistics have really validated the model and constrained the parameters. We can go one step further with his kind of modeling and actually try to use the merger histories of halos to connect galaxies over time. This is one example of this kind of approach, the work I did call the universe machine. This sort of takes the philosophy, but traces them through their histories and that actually allows you to directly connect the start formation histories with age -- with the history of dark matter. All of these kinds of approaches have given us that low red shifts some very consistent pictures where this plot shows a fraction of massive stars as a function of the Halo mass. You don't have to worry about what all of these different things are except for to say that basically every approach people have tried gives the same basic picture. The galaxy formation is not very efficient. It has a peak at a Halo mass that is roughly the mass of the Milky Way and its less efficient at lower. We use these models now in a very wide variety of kind of analyses and both astrophysics and cosmology. We can we can prioritize that Halo, galaxy Halo connection, cosmological ground, or to constrain dark matter physics, or we can model the galaxy Halo connection to make realistic realizations of large surveys. Or we can actually use those constraints to further constrain galaxy formations.

That now becomes a real industry. What have we learned from these kinds of approaches? I just want to briefly summarize what I think are a few highlights of what we actually have learned from this from the last decade or so of work from a very large number of people. First of all we learned that galaxy mass is really a large, connected to the dark matter halos. The scatter and stellar mass is small. Again, where is this tested. This is primarily tested low. Like I said before, we learned galaxy formation is an efficient and that speed is important with making it less efficient at both higher mass is above ten to the 12th and at lower masses, probably different kinds of feedback. All of these different kinds of methods seem to agree fairly well. When we can look at clustering, galaxy lensing, these are really important. We've also learned that a star formation, not just -- they start formation is most efficient and the little evolution with red shift. This is now mostly just tested by accounts. It's only tested with clustering and lensing which gives you a sanity check at very low. We have learned galaxy is a function of stellar mass and also a function of whether something is a central galaxy in a Halo versus a satellite and we know that galaxy quenching is also a function of red shift. A key thing that we learn is that they dark matter Halo, they really do seem to be the thing that is determining environmental galaxy formation. That means there is really two things that tell you what a galaxy is doing, if it's a central galaxy it's properties are driven primarily by Halo mass but if it's a satellite galaxy it's properties are driven by the mass of a central galaxy and by how long it has been hanging around in that dark matter Halo and influenced by that environment. This is a real shift in how we understand all of the properties of galaxies, now with a really deep, theoretical underpinning another thing that we have learned is that Halo mass is not enough. Things are more complicated. Sometimes this is called assembly bias, the basic idea that the clustering properties of dark matter Halo, subsequently of galaxies can, not only dependent on their mass, but also on their formation history or other properties like a concentration. And those uncertainties can really influence the galaxy clustering. I think there's now actually low red shift, but none of this has been tested beyond red shift one at all. Now back to the exciting topic of this meeting. Pretty much everything I told you is based on low red shift and that because at high red shift we have been focused on very small. To me the most exciting opportunity of the data that we are going to have from this telescope is to get these wide fields that are really enabling us to push those studies all the way to higher red shift. A couple of these plots in her talk on Monday, just to summarize, HST surveys have mapped out galaxy properties at high red shift very well. They have not been able to do that in a detailed way that we can do at low red shift where we have really tested the detail of the galaxy Halo connection. Because the clustering measurements are bigger than one or limited by a small field or because we haven't had lensing. To me what is really exciting is to sort of take this, these kinds of measurements that we have two connect one galaxy property to another galaxy property and put this fully in the cosmological context. The wide field with these detailed properties of galaxies will really enable us to do that. Basically put these things in a full context of not only the masses and environments of their halos, but their formation histories and how their mass assembles and connects that to things like the sizes, the Metallicity. I want to mention a few case studies of things I think are exciting. In the low universe, say a red shift of .5, we are able to actually measure the physical extent of dark matter Halo. This is something called the flash radius. What were talking about is an actual dynamical thing that is happening where galaxies are coming in from the Hubble, getting accreted on massive systems and there is an actual feature in the density profile that's visible in both the galaxy profile and the lensing profile. And in a recent study where we come minds these galaxy profiles with massive clusters we were actually able to show using a combination of observations and simulations, by giving that galaxy sample, the radius, the place where it is, indicating the average orbit of these galaxies is directly related to how long those galaxies have been in the Halo. That means if I look at right galaxies you can show that they have been in a Halo longer or they have different orbital properties. This serves as the clock. Here we are doing this at a red shift .5. If we are able to similar measurement with the Roman Space Telescope we will be able to do that from a red shift 1-3. Especially when combined with lensing and data. That would enable us to directly measure the coassembly of galaxies and dark matter halos over the peak of the star. To me that is really exciting. It's a real new framework for understanding how halos are formed and how that connects to the galaxy population. There will be a lot of new theoretical work that is needed. One is a consistent modeling framework that uses specifically motivated and observationally acceptable definition of dark matter halos, but also realistic simulation that allow code analysis. I will give one more example from strong lensing, this is an image from the slack survey of gravitational lenses. The Roman Space Telescope will provide something like 1,000 lenses with similar quality to HST. To give you a sense of what that would enable, right now we are talking about 23 lenses with HST images. And we now go from 23 to 1,000, it's going to enable really exciting things, both in astrophysics in terms of probing the feedback mechanisms that shape they dark matter and the luminous profile. Also jointly constraining the inner region of the stellar in the dark matter density profile. And then it also will be able to start to push further down the dark matter Halo mass function, hoping interaction properties of dark matter halos and measuring the function, down to roughly ten to the eighth over a wide range. I think this is

super exciting, but we will need a lot of modeling to really do this right here to really use the data to its full potential. I will say, what is exciting about measuring this Halo mass function, and the last couple of years a number of techniques and strong lensing with galaxies, two of the most exciting ones have actually started to push further down the mass function and start to probe things that are in the range of about ten to the eighth and ten to the ninth. What is exciting, many of you have probably seen this picture of how warm dark matter suppresses some structure compared to cold dark matter. It's not just warm dark matter. There is a wide possibility of models. It can be warm, fuzzy. Many things can suppress some structure. If you actually start to be able to measure those substructures with ten to the eighth, you can actually start to put really exciting constraints on a wide range of these models. The plot I'm showing here is from our recent work. Five more minutes. Okay. What is exciting is that the telescope will enable and vastly improved strong lensing. Okay Britt and my last few minutes, I want to say a little about lessons from the surveys and the simulations we been doing for cosmology surveys and how to design the realistic simulations. I want to give to example uses of simulations and analysis chain. First, when you use a realistic mock, the galaxy survey really as a test. When I say a test I mean for example running your whole pipeline to try to understand systematic, try to marginalize over those. And we have these very complex pipelines now, and both cosmology and galaxy formation studies where there is a whole bunch of moving parts and pieces that connect to each other. We really need to do and to and validation on a box that as realistic as possible. That way we can use realistic catalogs, not as a test, but as a model. What I mean by that is really doing direct forward modeling of key observables as a way to make predictions. I want to give a couple of examples that highlight what I mean by this. In terms of the mock as a test, the study that I've been working on it is with a dark energy survey. What we did with the data, and the your three data. We are doing realizations of the footprint with galaxy catalogs here, cluster catalogs, photometric redshifts, lensing, and these are realistic enough that we can really code analyzed them with the data. This is an example from our paper from last year and we will have a study coming out very soon come up the basic idea, we did 18 realizations of the footprint. And then we really ran every single piece of the pipeline, quenching, clustering, lensing, rent sample selection on those things to try to convince ourselves that we were getting the right cosmological. Galaxy formation studies are starting to push and in this direction. I don't think they have gotten as detailed as the cosmological simulation, but once our samples get larger and our statistical errors get smaller, these techniques will be really relevant for understanding our systematic errors and testing our pipeline. I also want to mention that both for cosmology and for galaxy evolution studies, modeling the complexities of multi-wavelength surveys is really going to be key. This is an example image from a really exciting piece of work that Yuuki worked on, dark matter halos, this is based on a multi-dark simulation. Combined with gravitational lensing and observables over the full sky. This is really exciting and I think this kind of thing is going to be needed as we pushed to the large samples of galaxies with the Roman Space Telescope. Briefly, I will mention this idea of using the mock as a model. An example that we been doing here is called the project, our goal is precision emulation of the statistics of dark matter halos and galaxies and their cross correlations. There's been expensive, extensive work. The basic idea is you run a simulation spanning the currently allowed parameter space and then you actually use those to predict to the directly and you interpolate the statistic within that space using the process and algorithm. Our philosophies with this work has been to try to be as lightweight as possible to get problems, emulators that are close to the data. For the papers we have already, a percent level estimate from the Halo mass function, what we were working towards as being able to predictions that actually are based on resolved Halo mergers and I think that's going to be quite relevant for the kinds of things were going to want to do and the Roman era. Where we really want to connect the history of galaxy evolution in their dark matter Halo with potentially synthetic Roman telescope imaging. And try to use those blocks directly as a way very briefly I will get two more examples of these pipelines that are happening right now one is, part of the thing that is really challenging here is we are trying to models which a wide range of observables and a wide range of skill. We took the kinds of simulation that week did for the dark energy survey and we combined them with spectroscopy that was relevant. We made predictions for the clustering. This specific analysis was to look at cosmology analysis and impact, the emission line on the signal. I think we are just starting to talk about similar techniques using the best data available to try to make predictions for galaxy evolution as well. Another really, really massive piece of work done by the dark energy science collaboration called data challenge. It combines cosmological simulations, galaxy models, with simulations on the camera. It's a really massive effort by a large set of people, really exciting because it allows you to connect those with the underlying cosmological. One more minute here. When we think about the biggest challenges in the era of the Roman Space Telescope, the power of the observation also means that we need the model. That's a very wide range of skills that are required and a wide range of physics that need to be included. Essentially the challenge is that because we can measure all of the correlation we really need to care about modeling. And that is incredibly hard. This is something I've been working on for 20 years really. And were making a

lot of progress, but there is a lot more to do to connect all of these different pieces in a really robust approach. Some of your techniques will be needed, direct modeling, emulators. And really being smart about how we combine different approaches, large cosmological simulations combined with detailed transfer on individual galaxies, combined with detailed modeling to really create these realistic mock catalogs. I will enter there. I want to leave you with two messages. The first is that we really do you have an powerful framework now I think understanding galaxy evolution in the context of star formation. We have extended that from her red shift ten to the presidents, using a very limited amount of data that's available at high redshifts. It's only very well tested, the low red shift is .5. It's very exciting that the Roman Space Telescope will enable detailed test with spatial cluster specifics. This will enable a wide range of galaxy properties including star formation rate, Metallicity, how are those connected to be underlined formation of dark matter? And then a second is that these surveys -- I think they are increasingly at the heart of how we understand data in the modern era and we really need to be creative because we are not yet at the stage where we can do massive simulations that have the same area and resolution of our data. We need to combine different approaches. I think there is a lot of exciting progress in those areas. Thank you. Thank you very much. Applause.

We have time for a very quick question from slack. Lorenzo, very great talk. I've a question. The standard definition of Halo mass is that of Brian and Norman, however as you're pointing out there is a quantity subject to the evolution and the radius is the real physical extent of the Halo. Our models based on the radii still valid? Fantastic question, very close to my heart. We just put in a big proposal to think about that harder. I agree with everything you said weird I think we now really understand that this flashback radius is the right physical radius to sort of distinguish between central and satellite and to account for what starts to happen with the star formation of galaxies once they enter a halo. However, most of the abundant work that I have done, it actually makes a really simple assumption that makes it better than you might expect. It is based on the old definition. Most of what the work that we have done is based on not assuming a difference between central and satellite. Assuming the properties of the Halo, the galaxies are set at their peak velocity. That is actually, that is basically the point where they start to get stripped which is the flashback. So we actually built that in some way to the abundant match. When we start to, and models like the universe machine when we talk about evolution, at a given snapshot, thanks for taking into account essentially the right radius. The evolution I think will, it will change our assumption of the mass accretion rate. I think the relationship between the star formation rate and the Halo mass rate will change when we change this definition. I think it's quite important and something I'm quite interested in. Thank you. If you can please go to the selected channel and answer and interact, answer the other questions. Thank you so much.

We are ready for the next speaker. Here you are. Nice to see you. Can you share your screen? She will talk about a mock catalogs for the Roman telescope ultra deep Field. Thank you. I am **Nicole Drakos**, I'm at UC Santa Cruz. One thing that we've been working on is making a mock galaxy catalog for an ultradeep field with the Roman telescope there is a really great talk Tuesday morning that went into detail, the survey what it will look like. The main points are it should be up to and beyond redshifts ten with a magnitude limited of 30 and cover an area of 1,000. This is a plot from of the paper with the exposure time with each of the filters to get to that limit of 30. And of course the really exciting thing about Roman telescopes is its wide view. This plot shows the field of view of the Roman Space Telescope compared to the HST cameras. In the area is about 100-200 times larger than HST and it will image more galaxies which will get better statistics and allow for us to see rare objects and it will allow us to probe environmental effects. This is just a plot that I made that shows the comparison of different surveys on the area. Something like the latitude survey is in the top left-hand corner where it has very large areas. And the deepest survey we have is the Hubble Ultra Deep Field which is the green point at the bottom. You can see it also has a very small area. And you should also note, Jade, the proposed deep field, it will do a lot better than humble and it will have a much larger area than the Roman, it will be a much larger improvement on that. They also course have different filters. This plot on the top is an example of a mock Spectra from the galaxy and it shows what the HST filter C as well as the other filter. I covered and read where the Roman telescope would fall on the plot. Some of the key science returned from the ultradeep field are high redshifts constraints on galaxy clustering, the UV a luminosity function, stellar mass functions. It will also allow us to look at ionizing sources around the RGM around the time of re-ionization. It will really be exciting for re-ionization. Also allows us to connect Lyman-L5 to the environment. I'm going to talk today about a mock galaxy catalog and the main effects of this is the science returned and the details. Secondly, we plan on releasing this so it can be used to help develop analysis and processing to this is an ongoing project as part of the

Expo team. And as a disclaimer a lot of the results I'm showing are preliminary. This is also a great opportunity to ask all of you if you have any suggestions or things you would like to see, if so contact me. You can message me on the select channel. This is a brief overview of the methods we use to create our catalog. We started with a simulation with the dark matter only simulation, 28 particles. And then we made a halo catalog. And we use this to build a halo light cone where we placed all the different halos where they will fall on the survey volume. We assigned galaxy masses through abundance matching. And then we used different relations and the literature with galaxy morphologies, to all the galaxy. The last that we plan on doing is to create a mock image. This is the next step so I don't have anything to show for that yet. Here is a visualization from the catalog. This shows the mass density. You can see from this with the details, this is 1 degree on the sky so at low red shift you don't expect too many galaxies because the volume is very low. And then as you go higher volume gets larger, but you see less stars because the density drops off. One of the first things we want to look into is how many galaxies would expect to detect from our mock catalog. This plot here shows the fraction of galaxies that will detect under the magnitude limit as a function of their mass and red shift. The black line is all of the galaxies and you can see once you get down, you would expect to see about 40% of them. Most of them being at the lower red shift, but once you are above galaxy masses of ten to the nine we expect you to detect most of the galaxies. So if we look at the number of galaxies expected with red shift, our predictions right now is that we expect them to be ten to the five and about a thousand Alex sees above red shift ten. That super exciting. Another thing that we want to know is how well we will be able to constrain the two-point correlation function of galaxies. This is a plot showing the correlation function from our mock galaxy catalog for galaxies in the range of 6-9 in the era of reorganization. This is the probability of two galaxies being separated by a radius of R_p . And from our catalogs we expect to constrain it within 30 percent which is pretty good. One thing we want to know if we can measure is the evolution of the clustering signal during re-ionization. This plot here shows the clustering, the angular clustering of the alpha emitters. Around redshifts thanks. And over top are these different lines, different neutral hydrogen fractions. So one of the RGM is very neutral you get a higher signal. We want to know whether we can measure this evolution which is all about re-ionization and the County catalog. Another interesting question is the luminosity function. This was talked about a lot in the Tuesday morning session. Here I applauded the number as detected, as well as the luminosity function. And one question about this is how the and evolves around high redshifts. Here is the plot by Rebecca Bowler that shows the current uncertainty in that part of the diagram. Here they have the current data points and the red line is the factor for you to it which is commonly used and the black dot is the power. You can see there is a large gap. One reason why that is interesting is because it is connected to universes and it would tell us a lot about galaxy formation if we could get better constraints on it. In conclusion, the Roman telescope ultradeep field will have a large field of view which will allow to measure things like environmental effects around galaxies. We are currently working on a mock galaxy catalog. Some of our predictions, a thousand but red shift ten. And that we should be able to constrain the clustering signal and we might also be able to study re-ionization through mentors. And also we should be able to get good constraints on how the UV luminosity functions. Great. Thank you very much. I can take questions now. Thank you, Nicole. Virtual applause for you. I will ask a quick question. You mentioned you are planning to model the images of the galaxies which would be very exciting. Your plans, once you plan to do that? Hopefully within the next few months. We plan on using that come I've looked into detail on how I will use that yet. Okay. There might be more questions coming on the select channel. I encourage you to go there and interact with the other speakers and with the rest of the participants. Thank you again.

We can move onto the the next speaker. John Weaver. While you pull up your screen he will talk about the catalog for the next generation of galaxy surveys.

Hi, everyone. My name is **John Weaver**, I am a PhD student at the University of Copenhagen. Thank you for giving me the opportunity to speak with you all today. It's been really exciting hearing all the discussions and work over the past week. I think it's really exciting for the next decade. I want to take a few moments of your time to discuss the Cosmos survey and an particular the catalog that we have prepared. And its role as a stepping stone into the next generation and preparing for the next generation. I want to thank my collaborators, especially Olivia who together with myself prepared the catalog. Just a quick overview of Cosmo's. It's the deepest wide survey on the sky with 20 years of extensive multi-wavelength observations from x-ray come and for read all the way to the radio. It has an enormous community of astronomers over a thousand astronomers working to preserve the observation time for it and it has

extraordinary sample and due to its depth it is uniquely suited for a large scale structure as well as pioneer models to map out dark matter structure. With all this wonderful science and breakthrough innovation in the field, it's selected as a deeper calibration field for the next generation of galaxy surveys, most notably, to name a few. I also want to point out that in cycle 28 is a 3D program which will cover 1.7 square degrees of Cosmo's. I think that's really exciting and we can look forward to that. Now to the catalog. Here I show the footprints of the primary surveys that constitute the catalog. We have the cloud data and purples. Then we have the green. And then the prime and blue which provided the broadband, the backbone of the 2015 catalog and its intermediate band, useful indicators for the 2020 catalog as well. There is of course the ultra Vista coverage which is shown in red. And we also include the full archival coed of IRAC. Just to get a sense of how large it is, I compare it to the full moon and some of the surveys we've been discussing earlier this week on the right-hand side. As they said on Monday, both catalog and pixel level data sets provide unique opportunities. I think in the catalog we have really gone a long ways to take advantage of that fact. We have 1 billion pixels of image data with over 39 bands. Out of that we've selected, and for red band to select a catalog of 1 million galaxies over to square degrees. To show you the depth on the bottom right, the coverage is shown in the Graybar. You can see we've made significant gains and depth and the optical as well as the marginal gain and channel one and two. Just to give you an idea of what this means, of course it means extreme density, especially from ground-based observation Subaru. I show and the top right-hand side a cut out from the image, a really gorgeous galaxy there, but also to give you a sense of how rich these fields are and how dense they are. And what kind of challenges they pose for us as, you know, extraction and making these catalogs. I get to my point. The surveys are pushing methods past their breaking point. What do I mean by that? On the left-hand side I show Subaru image from the cosmos. You can see how there is a density, but it doesn't look that bad. Now compare that to the lifelines to understanding the formation and assembly of the highest galaxies, we have to be able to contend with this kind of crowd data. And so we must develop new tools and continue to develop existing tools to achieve greater blending and supporting diagnostics. Or we will forfeit our ability to robustly measure the faintest and most distant galaxies. And so as they said on Monday, we can do better in the era of big data. I hope to show over the next few slides that we have embraced these ideas already. We utilize parametric models to fit our sources using the tractor here decode made by Dustin and David which has been used in the decal survey. And just to remind folks what I mean by parametric models here, position or no model parameter. We are not performing any homogenization or apertures whatsoever. What do we gain from this? By leveraging our understanding of galaxy models and morphology we can better separate noise from a genuine source flux in the regime of ultra faint sources to regain that sensitivity. We also gain superior blending, I demonstrate that on the right-hand side showing an image from two galaxies and an image from Subaru for which we made a model. And then by using that same model which is solving, leaving its flux to the perimeter we achieve a model for channel one that will describe the image. And to compare that with, you can see how the models perform easily what is a struggle with Aperture. And we get a free lunch out of this, there is free statistics like this, as well as residual statistics such as a distribution of the pixel as well as measurements of galaxy shape and sizes. I think that will be a particularly powerful advantage over the next decade. But of course all good things have their downside. It is slow going. We are not your summing up pixels and apertures. We have developed a framework for high computing called the farmer to drive the tractor. The farmer provides detection modeling and catalog creation so the input output is similar to the extractor. To demonstrate the richness of this model-based approach I show you two images. One is a real image taken from Subaru. The other one is a model of which we've added a little bit of noise because we didn't want to make it too easy for you. I want you to take a moment and look at the two images and try to figure out which one is the model and which one is the actual image. While you do that I like to advertise a talk on Friday, using the farmer code with tractor to the north ecliptic pole. On the left-hand side is the model and the right-hand side or the real galaxy. I think that's a really cool demonstration. Of course we need to validate, images are cool but we have to make sure were getting that right. We are going to benchmark the farmer against the extractor. We have prepared a catalog, we call it classic. We find excellent agreement. On the right-hand side I show a selection of broadband filters which are prominent and narrowing down red shifts. I show the 2D distribution, described by a median with a 60% range and dribble out to the depth limit which is marked by that vertical line. And then with the dotted grade curve are the one sigma and three Sigma uncertainty we would expect colors are also consistent with less than 5% range. I show a couple over here to give you an idea. Given our excellent photometric agreement we also use to put electric codes, aligning both of them to each of our tests. The photometric rent shift obtained with the codes, with the catalog for a given photometric rent shift code are extremely similar. I demonstrate that on the top row with LePhare, with the magnitude on the right. We see that we have excellent agreement with the exception of these two forms that shoot out and that is due to confusion with this problem with the photometric code fitting techniques. I also note that the photometric code themselves produce

extremely similar results which is very nice to see. You take away message though is that we have achieved an unprecedented photometric accuracy with the Sigma less than 1% on the bright end less than 5% to end. I demonstrate that on the right-hand side here in the lower two rose. On the same two topics, comparing LePhar to the red shifts. 2 minutes. Thank you. We have extremely similar results, really good Sigma, low bias and failure rate as well. Promising moving forward. Where will we go forward? Now we have four Cosmo catalogs. That means we have multiple independent measurements of photometry, red shift, stellar masses and star formation rates and rest frame magnitudes. And so I draw your attention to this source on the right-hand side where we have measured class again farmer. And while the LePhar code which we have used for this particular example finds the classic photometry a peek solution. The farmer code produces a single pixel solution favoring the higher red shift. If you look at the cut outs here you will notice what is right when the distance is really in the optical thread where there is a lot of noise, but also crowding by nearby sources that might travel the optical measurements and increase the flux more than what you see in farmer. So they take away here is that the model based photometry is really going to be critical with reaching the universe in the area of the ultradeep, white surveys such as Roman. Finishing up, the catalog is slated to be released in early 2021. It will contain a sample of about 1 million galaxies measured and 39, many more and fewer. With this innovative model based photometry with the farmer as well as the classic approach we have shown excellent agreement with the aperture techniques and we have shown that we can understand the systematic with the multiple measurements provided by the multiple methods and photometric code, and in the end we have achieved the unprecedented red shift accuracy scatter and bias. Which demonstrates the cosmos has a wonderful stepping-stone in developing the next generation of galaxy surveys so that we can get the best science field. Before I wrap up I want to point out that cosmos 2025 will see coverage by Rubin and Euclid, and who knows, maybe even Roman. Thank you very much. Thank you. Virtual applause.

We have a few questions on slack. I will pick the two that have been liked by other people. We have the first Mark. He's asking, models do not properly model complex morphology, this is not a problem for ground-based data but it can become a problem at the high spatial resolution. Could you comment on that? Yes. As we gain spatial resolution we diverge in our model space, and our perimeter space between our models and our data. And exactly as he puts it, yes, as the resolution gets better, you are simple, smooth profile won't do. Looking at things like that might be a solution. That is a fundamental limitation here. While the code is extremely useful with the data, as you will notice we didn't apply it for those reasons. Thanks. I hope that answers your question otherwise we can talk more on slack. Feel free to go to the channel.

I will ask you another question. Another question. This was liked. Are they classified as stars and if so, how are they selected just size or size and other? Star galaxy separation as selected by mixture between the SCD and size, that work is Premier LI done by the photometric. Yeah, we've explored a variety of star galaxy separation techniques and we found the most useful one is to follow the SED with sizes, noting the different ranges and magnitude are different than resolution, limiting one of those two approaches. I believe were following on the same methodologies and the 2015 star galaxy. Thanks. Thank you very much. We will stop now. Please go back to the slot channel and answer the Questions.

We will move to Prerak Garg. I don't think I can hear you. No. Audio is not coming. If you don't mind you can troubleshoot this. And we can have the other talk first. Okay. Aritra Ghosh? I can see you. I can hear you. Aritra Ghosh from Yale will talk about morphology and quenching of galaxy in the Roman Space Telescope era using a network. Take it away.

Hello, everyone. I am **Aritra Ghosh**. I'm a fourth year PhD student at the Department of astronomy at Yale University. Let me first thank the organizers for putting on this fantastic conference. I really enjoyed listening to all the talks and conversations on slack. Today I will be talking to you about how the solution to study morphology and quenching in large data sets and such that we used by the Roman Space Telescope where it let me begin by saying why. Morphology isn't interesting in their own right, but let me start with the simulation of two disk galaxies. As you all know, they do not survive the mergers. If you see a disk galaxy you can be pretty sure that they did not have a major. In a sense you can use the morphology of a galaxy as a proxy for its module. How does that help us to understand the galaxy evolution? To make my point to let me start with this color diagram of the galaxies at red shift is zero. We

know from the data that galaxies occupy model distribution. You have this blue cloud of star-forming galaxy and you have the red sequence of quench galaxy and between you have a lack of galaxies. The standard paradigm and application of this diagram used to be that the galaxies in the blue are quenched rapidly into the red. Now if you bring morphology into this picture you get sort of a different understanding of this scenario. This was done as an galaxy to become shift to zero. And what they found is two different evolutionary parts. For the disk they find they reach a critical Halo mass at which they show science. After formation there quenched rapidly through the Green Valley. So you are bringing in morphology to the picture you kind of uncover these two separate evolutions. Showing how morphology may be interesting other than just in its own right, how interesting it is with the galaxy. They said this was done at red shift to zero. However, an order to understand the galaxy evolution and the peak of star formation, such analysis needs to be performed at large higher redshifts on large samples. The Roman Space Telescope due to its resolution and view is the perfect tool to do this. Now let's talk about a few methods you can use to detect morphology of galaxy. Each technique has its own pros and cons and its own case. However, if you are going to do a large statistical study of morphology on a large sample of galaxies and the best technique that you can use is to use the method. However, essentially, let's assume that you were going to use a network, you will produce morphology catalog of all the galaxies that will be seen by Roman. There is a catalog itself, the output of the network data from where you get your training data to train your method. Essentially you get stuck in this chicken and egg problem of what comes first and what you will do first when you're trying to use a convolutional method on a brand-new surface. And to address this we double up the network of galaxy morphology and the main power and the fact that it does not require too much real training data can be applied to galaxies across varying ratios, meaning galaxies at different redshifts and from different surface and all the models as well as the source code is available. We try to write this code and make it available in a way so that it's very easy to download and use through the perspective of if you're trying to train you are models or use one of our pretrained models. Let's come to how we train. To benchmark the performance we select to samples -- the galaxies at red shift. We start with a set of parameters that is typical, using those parameters we stimulate, emulate galaxies and now using these galaxies and the labels generated from the parameters we train the network to classify them. Now add the final step, we take this network which has always been trained on simulation and then use a small part of the real data to find, fine-tuning the already trained network. And once this is done we have a trained NetWare if you feed the image it gives you how it is dominated. I will come back and explain what it is in a second, but first let's look at the results. For both samples at a zero and one, with net accuracy of more than 95%. As you can see the lowest accuracy that we achieved our for the bulge. We wanted to investigate this, why this is the case. Let me try to show this to you using the histograms of signal to noise ratio and radii which are products for the galaxy as well as the current example. As you can clearly see, the misclassified example has a low signal to noise ratio and a radii which is almost comparable to the survey. And it's important to point out here that we did not implement any quality there. We wanted to see out of the box how does our network perform? If we do impose quality regarding to the signal to noise ratio, then the net accuracy numbers that I showed you earlier go up even further. Let's finally come back full circle and let me show you the color map diagram. And so for both we see that this dominated galaxy is across a broad range of showing the decrease with the red sequence with low distortion of gas at higher masses we see more galaxies about 14% of all of the red shift to zero and 2% of all of this that redshifts one. Testing the high Halo mass plays a role. In contrast, for the bulge donated galaxies we see their mostly red with much smaller numbers down to the cloud so there is rapid quenching across the Green Valley into the red sea. This is shown by the depth of numbers. And using the convolutional narrow network really allowed us to have a larger sample and in a sense allowed us to get very good statistics even and sparsely populated parts of the color diagram such as the bulge galaxies at red shift one. Now having shown to you our findings both in terms of accuracy and the diagram let me try to explain -- tell you the last minute about why you should believe the results of the convolution area neural network event why GaMorNet is not a box as is often perceived. To do that let me start with something that I promised I will do. I will explain -- sorry, in case you are not convinced by the scatterplot. Let me start by explaining. What we do exactly in the process of transfer learning as we take the entire network which has already been trained on simulations and then we find two and only the last few layers based on real data. Why do we do this? What is the logic? The reasoning is how networks work. I will show you the different filter patterns, eventually these are the structures or the patterns that the network is trying to look for as we go deeper and deeper. As you can see very early on the network is trying to look for a very simple features like lines, shapes, and edges. If we go a little bit deeper, it needs to look for circles which are important parts of the image. It's only in the final sets of layer that the network is looking at the very detailed features, for example here it's trying to look for spiral, it's trying to look for, what is the live distribution in the center of the galaxy compared to the outskirts? And since it is only the final few layers that take the last steps that are taking the high level decisions, you only need to

find tune the last few layers because you explain the simulation is not good enough. It would be as realistic. This shows that GaMorNet is not a box but it takes an image and goes through this hierarchical position process of arriving at the final. 2 minutes. Thank you. Let's take this question further and ask, okay, I know that it takes an image, what are some of the intermediate steps? As you can see and some of the intermediate outputs which are shown over here, the output are closer to the -- the initial layers you can see what is happening is that the network is clearly subtracted the galaxy out from the background that is shown by these images. It is pulled to galaxy from the background and it's trying to look at some parts of the image trying to analyze each part, showing that hierarchal digital part. The final test for what we use with activation, asking the network, okay, they dominated galaxy, now tell me what part? What we find for example here for these two galaxy networks, you take the right parts, with the network that was important. We see the network traces all the spirals because it thinks it's a very important feature. On the other hand as is shown over here which we are trying to show, if there are other galaxies in the frame, the network property learns to not focus on these, but instead focus on the galaxies. Hopefully I have convinced you that GaMorNet are not flat boxes but they are easy to inspect. GaMorNet can do composition across a large range of ratios and redshifts. While the results are publicly available, it gives us the example of morphology with the diagrams showing up with the evolution. All these results are published and so there from 2019 primarily, but what we have been working on right now is extending GaMorNet so it can do predictions of distributions of different morphologies with the light ratio and we are combining GaMorNet with a network so that we can also study galaxy and active. Thank you. I will take questions. Thank you. Virtual applause.

We have a couple of questions from the select panel. I will read you the ones. Awesome talk. Really interesting work. Question one, do you have data on how fast and accurate it is with GaMorNet with the visioning section or the science approach -- excuse me, science project? A second question, what are the concerns with biases versus those that are due to the observed training sample volume limited? Thank you for the question. In terms of comparing this to the project, I think the accuracy, we did not compare -- for example we did not take our results and compare it against either the galaxy to candle. That is a session I think we can do. I cannot answer. I would say there could be as accurate. The difference primarily is in terms of when you get galaxy results you need to spend a lot of time and understanding, the galaxies, you spend a lot of time devising. I think these two processes are slightly different with how you approach. It's a very good point and I will probably look into this with how much we agree with the galaxies.

And a second question I think was asking the difference between simulations and realistic data. It is not the question? This is the step. Interesting relations with super real steps and then we would not need that. We need that transfer because the simulations that we have used for GaMorNet are not as realistic. We have been spending some time looking into exactly what the network is learning with those last few steps. To characterize what is the additional thing that we don't have. I think there are a few things the network learns. One thing that an simulations you make very clean snapshots. Not having other galaxies. In a future network what we are working on right now, the network on the slide, to focus on the galaxy. In addition there are final differences as we have discussed, final differences between simulations and the real data which kind of forces us to have that. I can talk to you more on slack about that. Awesome. Thank you very much. You will have some work to do on the slack channel. Thank you again.

Let's go back to **Prerak Garg** and see if everything is working now. We can hear you. We can see the screen and we can see the slides. We have Prerak Garg modeling nebular emission and cosmological galaxy formation simulations.

I'm a fourth year graduate student. Today I will be talking about nebular emission and cosmological galaxy formation simulations. My collaborators are here. The aim of the project is to combine cosmological simulations and provide modeling, create a system model with nebular V-8 and this can be used to study a host of them. The plan of the talk is very straightforward. I want to answer one question, what drives the PPT offset at high speed five? What is a BPT diagram? It's a diagnostic tool used for nebular line ratios. Here I'm going to show you the diagram with the ratio. To classify galaxies. The second part of the question is the offset at high redshifts. In recent years as they have been observed in higher galaxies, these galaxies are on the diagram. Here I'm showing the galaxy, whereas the other survey are shown here. In these galaxies follow different things and the physical mechanism behind the offset is unclear. There is no one consensus behind it. These are base model assumptions. We assume a constant density. Only less than ten and the simulation -- with the galaxies forming, to the population and depending on what star

particles, these are cloudy. This is where the model differs itself from the other models. We learn how these particles have worked -- once we have nebular emission we can transfer out. And all of these different work together -- so this is an example of what it looks like. And then the profile. Now that I've explained to you how our models work you can do a BPT diagram. To do that we use hydrodynamic simulation. We are using the size of 25 particles with a mass resolution of about six LMS. This is what it looks like, here I'm showing the color-coded -- and -- as we can see galaxies are in the same space as the other, but to quantify this it is important that the lines came away from the Metallicity space as well. What do we do with it? We draw a point. Take all of the galaxies that lie within this box and then see how far -- ideally it should be as close as possible. From what we get is the following. We find that around these galaxy, the Metallicity -- this makes us very confident that our model can get observations. Going forward, I smooth out the galaxy using a model like this and I approximate galaxies -- so now I am confident the models can get zero snap shot, we move ahead to see what happens in high redshift. We get the following. Overhear the redline is showing the area -- and then we can see the blue density plot is here. They do not move towards the offset. The obvious question was, why aren't we seeing the offset? We decided rather than doing it -- experiments to see if we can pinpoint the reason behind it. Coming back to the question of what drives the BPT offset at high redshifts? High ionization parameter or harder radiation fields, or higher ratio. We decided to test these one by one. First the higher ionization parameter. We can find that by following this -- and the strongest radius. And what we do is we change the number of protons to increase or decrease. In blue you are seeing the shift, through the base model and where we decrease shown in green and red. The important point or the take away point is if we increase or decrease, but does not move towards the offset. All of this was done by manually changing. We decided to look at what it really depends on. The protons -- we look at -- including that can be increasing the number. We even looked at changing the density. And we came to a similar conclusion. It does not account for it. We ruled this out and then we move forward to the next question, the harder radiation. In order to do that we decided to include stellar rotation. On the Y axis I'm showing the number with hydrogen. This connected -- and then you can see including the stellar rotation does produce something more. We include this into our model we do find that in general the ratio increases but the scale does not -- the next part is we decided to include binary stars using the model grid. It is shown here in the green. That is on X axis. So when we include these models what we get business. We see it reveals, but in essence does not move -- this led us to conclude that the higher ratio cannot pretty next part was to look at higher ratios. There have been studies that have shown the nitrogen ratio can involve, this is a plot in 2020 with a local analog with higher galaxy. it has shown -- might have a higher analog. In order to test it what we did is we first of all, and are base model we took the value -- and then we increased the ratio and steps of .2. What you see is when it increases it starts moving to the right which is expected. By increasing the ratio. And it increases by about .4, so really overlaps. In essence the higher ratio seems to be the explanation. I started with the question, what offset at the higher redshifts? The higher does seem to offer it. There are some caveats to our model. Diffused ionized gas. Right now we assume -- absorbed but clearly some of it leaks out. Studies have shown that this can account for a large collection. We do not include dust within the region so the dust in the galaxy is taken into account, but the regions are dust free. You do not a dynamic model. Two more minutes. Okay. Thank you. We do not include AGN's or post AGB stars. And metal enrichment due to stellar rotation and binary interruptions. Stellar rotations with material can increase changing. We do not include -- into the model. In terms of how this model will play a role in the era of the Nancy Grace telescope. This has a bigger sample and strong lines with one of the basic methods by which Metallicity are -- the galaxy Metallicity is not complete. All of this integration has been done, but simulations can play a really important role. For example, it should not be used when getting Metallicity from the hydrogen galaxy. In summary, we have uploaded the model on a particle basis. This is really a step forward. Our models can reproduce the red shift. It's no different than. Sorry. You caught out for a second. Have you gone through all your summaries? Yes. Great. Virtual applause for you as well. We have a few questions in the slack channel. I will go with the question from Andrea. If I understood correctly, your Metallicity and ionization, can your model be used to figure out what create some of the inner high edge low Metallicity profiles yesterday? That's a good question. I don't have a direct answer to that. How reliable can that be is the question in itself. For example, there is a law question about how do you think nitrogen abundances, secondary, and for our models we look at changing that to figure it out, but in the end I don't have a really good answer for this. I'm not sure. Okay. We will take another question. What is the physical origin of the announcement? They are different. One, this can be very consequential evolving the simulation. The effect you are seeing higher, the other -- this showed, it showed that the higher -- you can get the star rate and a high star formation rate. As far as I know there is no one pinpoint reason for why this is happening, but it's in areas like the scenarios. Great. Thank you. Go back to the channel and answer the other questions.

This concludes our session. Please stick around because we have a poster session after this and I guess they will take over now. Thank you to all the afternoon speakers. I want to leave you with a few announcements. I want to remind the speakers to upload your files, your slides, to the Box. You can also upload them to slack in your session channel. For those of you who have not yet presented we will be having speaker ready sessions this afternoon at 4:30p.m.-5:00 p.m. on blue jeans events. Log back in as a presenter. Also tomorrow morning between 9-9:30 a.m. Again, to remind you to visit the posters and enjoy the interactive discussions that are occurring on there. If you are a speaker please do remember to check your channel for more questions and answer sessions. This concludes our oral session for today. Remember, visit the posters between 2-3. Thank you and see you tomorrow.

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